

Machine-Learned Data Compression for Outer Solar System Missions

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Outline

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2. Supplementing transform coding with ML
3. Generalizing Transform-Based Compression with Neural Networks
4. Image Sequence Compression Using Optical Flow
5. Using Adversarial Discriminator Networks to Distinguish between Compression Error and Noise

Case Study: The Cassini Imaging Subsystem

Reference: Porco et al., 2004

The Cassini Imaging Science Subsystem (ISS) is the highest-resolution two-dimensional imager on the Cassini Orbiter and was designed for investigations of the bodies and phenomena within the Saturnian planetary system.

Problems with Lossy Compression on Cassini ISS

Original

Compressed (JPEG)
Displays Visible Artifacts

An Improved Customized Compressor

- A study was performed to assess how highly Cassini ISS data could have been compressed without harming science retrievals, determined by the science team.
 - Reference: Xia, West, Seignovert, Jewell, Kurth, Averkamp, 2021
- Found that by selecting well-chosen transform-based compressors, the images could be compressed at higher ratios without harm.

Example: Saturn and Rings

Original

Wavelet
decompressed

Wave atom
decompressed

Estimated
intrinsic noise

Wavelet
compression
error

Wave atom
compression
error

- Intrinsic noise was estimated by the difference between original image and median filtered version.
- The power of the noise and error images are shown in logarithmic scale.
- Compression error fell below the intrinsic noise level even at CR of $\sim 10:1$.

Reference: Xia, West, Seignovert, Jewell, Kurth, Averkamp, 2021

Our Vision

1. Update the paradigm by which we perform compression
 - Currently, a fixed compressor is supplied, and science teams may decide whether or not to use it.
 - Often leads to overly conservative compression.
2. Produce a facility compressor that hosts several algorithms and has input from compression experts.
 - Ease burden on science teams and allow for infusion of state-of-the-art compression expertise.
 - Science teams can build and fine-tune a custom compressor with our tools.
3. Allow science teams to upload new algorithms and change parameters during the mission based on knowledge gained.
 - May require isolation from the rest of the spacecraft to allow for uploads and a fast turnaround.

Supplementing Wavelet Compression with Machine Learning

- In our original wavelet-based compression, we select an appropriate wavelet transform, and keep a subset of the transform coefficients deemed most significant.
- Reducing the number of coefficients yields a higher compression ratio, but can lead to unacceptable image reconstruction error.
- We have identified several uses of machine learning to enhance this algorithm:
 1. Neural network compression of residual image error
 2. Optimizing the wavelet transform parameters
 3. Simultaneously compressing multiple flyby images
- Goal: Allow for network training/testing on ground using initial data download. Then upload network parameters to compressor.

Residual Image Error Compressor

A single iteration of the networks used to encode/decode image residuals after applying wavelet-based compression. The network applies a series of convolutional and recurrent convolutional layers to compress and decompress a 32x32 image subsection. Each iteration compresses the reconstruction error with respect to the previous one. By default, we apply this network for 8 iterations, adding a total of 1 bit per pixel.

Neural Network Compression of Residual Image Error

Left: Original image (Titan Haze).

Center: Error in the reconstructed image from storing 3% of the coefficients of the db5 wavelet transform (compressing by a factor of 8.33).

Right: Error using only 1% of the db5 coefficients, with neural network assistance (a compression factor of 9.8). This eliminates most compression artifacts while achieving a higher compression rate.

Improved Effect on Haze Retrieval

Pixel values of original and reconstructed images of Titan haze. Applying the network to the image residual after storing 1% of the db5 wavelet coefficients, we recover the signature “detached haze bump” outlined in the red box, compressing by an overall factor of 9.8. Without neural network assistance, we fail to recover the detached haze even when storing ten times as many coefficients, compressing only by a factor of 2.5.

Fixing Problems with Original Transform Algorithm

- Subsection of image of Tethys (high-spatial-entropy).
- Using our original method, we see noticeable compression artifacts, and we lose some features of the original topography of the image.
- This example compresses to ~ 3 bpp.

Wavelet Transform Neural Network

Original Image

Four convolutional kernels applied to original image

Iteratively apply four new convolutional kernels to the first output from the previous level

Collect the outputs from all secondary (blue) levels, as well as the final primary (orange) level, into a single vector

Above: The encoder network, E . We construct a corresponding decoder network D with independent trainable transposed convolutional layers.

Minimizing Distortion, Maximizing Compression

$$\text{minimize } \|X - \mathcal{D} \circ \mathcal{E}(X)\|_2 + \lambda \cdot L(\xi | \mathcal{E}(X))$$

Minimized Loss Function:

A linear combination of the image reconstruction error and the negative log likelihood of the modeled distributions given the transformed coefficients (a surrogate for differential entropy).

Blue:
Original transformed coefficients

Orange:
Quantized coefficients

We quantize the transformed coefficients and apply entropy coding.

Coefficient Encoding

Vectorized Image Patches

For the i^{th} encoded coefficient, select a quantization interval δ_i to be fixed for all patches.

Quantization Map:

$$Q_i^{(\delta_i)}: y_i \mapsto q_i := \left\lfloor \frac{y_i - \mu_i}{\delta_i} \right\rfloor,$$

Coefficient Estimation Map:

$$\hat{y}_i := \mu_i + \delta_i \cdot \left(Q_i^{(\delta_i)}(y_i) + \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

We will use an arithmetic coder to encode all the i^{th} coefficients at once. Ideally, choose $\mathbf{d} := [\delta_1, \dots, \delta_N]^T$ to minimize reconstruction error at a requested estimated bit rate.

Solution:

- Steepest descent minimization with respect to \mathbf{d} of the average discrete entropy of each quantized coefficient, $\sum H(q_i) / N$.
- Halt the minimization at the desired estimated bits per pixel.

Example: The Icy Satellite Tethys

- The details of the image are better preserved, and the dynamic range of the error is 2-4 times smaller, even at higher compression factors than our original algorithm.
- For reference: lossless JPEG compression achieves 4.36 bpp.

Example: Propellers in Saturn's Rings

- Machine-learned compression successfully reconstructed propellers.
- Lower MSE than original wavelet algorithm between 0.6-1.75 bpp.
- More accurate reconstructions than original algorithm at higher bpp.
 - Explanation: The ML compressor learns the underlying signal, and devotes more significant bits to reconstructing it.

Original Image: 12 bpp

Neural-Network-
Compressed Image: 1.53 bpp

ML-Assisted Image Sequence Compression

- Tethys Flyby Sequence
- For certain flyby image sequences, we can apply video compression techniques to boost our compression factor and reduce our reconstruction error.

Correlating Successive Images

Image 1

Image 2, translated for maximum correlation with Image 1

Residual

Implementing a correlation-maximizing image translation aligns the high-entropy images of Tethys well enough that we can nearly predict the second from the first.

Combining Image Prediction with Wavelet and Residual Neural Network Compression

Left: Original image subsection from a flyby sequence for Tethys.

Center: Reconstruction using 1% of wavelet coefficients and the neural network assistance (CF = 9.8)

Right: Reconstruction using earlier images to predict current one. We compress the prediction error using only 0.5% of wavelet coefficients and neural network residual compressor. Overall CF rises to 12.1, and we are able to resolve some of the finer topographic features of the image, as well as reduce compression artifacts.

Spatial Pyramidal Network To Estimate Optical Flow

Fine Tuning Optical Flow Estimation

A) Image Patch 1

B) Image Patch 2
(Maximally-
correlated
translation)

C) Initial error
using Image 1 to
predict Image 2.

D) Error after warping
Image 1 using machine-
learned optical flow. Fine-
tuned network produces
lower error at the cost of
more bits per pixel
(~4.68 bpp for opt. flow)

Balancing Optical Flow Compression with Residual Error Compression

Initial residual error after optical flow correction (optical flow compressed to ~ 1.2 bpp)

Estimated and compressed/restored residual error (an additional ~ 1.2 bpp)

Final residual error

Effect on Entire Tethys Image

Original Image
(12 bpp)

Machine-learned wavelet
compression (~2.95 bpp)

Machine-learned optical
flow/residual compression
(~2.69 bpp)

Using a Discriminator Network

- A simple convolutional network tasked with classifying a residual as “compression error” or “noise” given the original image.
- We aim to use this to determine whether the image has been compressed to within the noise level.

Training Compressor and Discriminator Adversarially

Adversarial Discriminator Network Results

- The compressor/decompressor successfully reconstruct the main features of the image, with a reconstruction error more closely matching our assumed noise model.

Original Image

Compressed/reconstructed
using neural network encoder
trained against an adversarial
discriminator network,
compressing to 1.54 bpp

Reconstruction Error

Next Steps

- Train larger networks on larger image patches, or on full images.
- Use discriminator network to flag regions which require more bits per pixel to eliminate compression error.
- Demonstrate algorithms on high-TRL hardware
- Produce user-friendly software to allow teams to easily use our tools.
- Collaboration at the project level, and integration into the data science community.